

REPORT:

A4.3.9

Deliverable D8:

“Best practice guide on how to build an optimised multi-infusion

set-up to ensure the most effective dosing of a combination of drugs and fluids with different viscosities, including guidance on check valves and other components that benchmark stability in flow rates”

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This report was written as part of activity A.4.3.9 from the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery (MeDD II) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2019 and focused on providing traceable measurements of volume, flow and pressure of existing drug delivery devices and mixing behaviour and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems. For more details about this project, please visit www.drugmetrology.com.

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Introduction to the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery project

The overall aim of this project is to improve dosing accuracy and to enable the traceable measurement of volume, flow and pressure in existing drug delivery devices and in-line sensors operating at very low flow rates. This will be achieved through the development of new calibration methods and by expanding the existing metrological infrastructure. This project will also investigate fast changing flow rates, which are step changes between two flow rates within a second, the physical properties of mixtures of liquids and occlusion phenomena in multi-infusion systems in order to prevent inaccurate measurement results and thus to improve patient safety.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop new traceable techniques for generating and measuring the response or delay time of drug delivery devices regarding changes in flow rate, from 5 nL/min to 100 nL/min, using Newtonian liquids (WP1). For steady flow rates an uncertainty of 1 % ($k=2$) or better is expected, whereas for fast changing flow rates an uncertainty of 2 % ($k=2$) or better is expected. The techniques developed will be used to characterise and validate the different response times of at least 3 different types of drug delivery devices (including infusion analysers) (WP3 and WP4) and one type of flow sensor, to accurately measure the administered flow and volume with the required uncertainties.
2. To upgrade the existing flow facilities and knowledge of the partner NMIs in order to enable the traceable in-line measurement of the dynamic viscosity of Newtonian liquids, as a function of the flow rate and pressure difference, with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$). The measurement uncertainty will be validated using Newtonian liquids with traceable dynamic viscosity calibration. Additionally, tests with non-Newtonian liquids will be performed in order to prove the concept. To calibrate transfer standards for the in-line measurement of dynamic viscosity and other physical properties of liquids, in order to use these transfer standards for flow measurement and to determine the mixing behaviour of different liquids.
3. To develop and validate novel calibration procedures for existing medical flow devices (e.g. infusion pumps, pain controllers and infusion pump analysers) with traceability to a primary standard and with a target uncertainty value of 2 % ($k=2$) for a range of 5 nL/min up to 600 ml/min and also to develop a proof-of-concept on-chip microfluidic pump used as a transfer standard in drug discovery and organ-on-a-chip applications for flow rates lower than 100 nL/min.
4. To design and develop a multi-infusion system containing check valves, with several options for testing how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration. The flow rates and pressures will be traceably calibrated in all infusion lines, as well as at the outlet of the syringe pump, to be able to analyse the effects of pressure-equalising devices and to detect occlusion phenomena and bad mixing configurations.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (i.e. accredited laboratories, instrumentation manufacturers, etc.), standards developing organisations (ISO/TC 30, ISO/TC 48, ISO/TC/SC 62D, ISO/TC 69, ISO/TC 76, ISO/TC 84, ISO/TC 150, ISO/TC 210) and end-users (i.e. hospitals and health centres).

Activity 4.3.9 – Deliverable D8 - Best practice guide on how to build an optimised multi-infusion set-up to ensure the most effective dosing of a combination of drugs and fluids with different viscosities, including guidance on check valves and other components that benchmark stability in flow rates.

This report was developed using inputs from A4.3.1-A4.3.7, UMCU, NEL, METAS and THL in order to produce a best practice guide on how to build an optimised multi-infusion set-up to ensure the most effective dosing of a combination of drugs and fluids with different viscosities, including guidance on check valves and other components that benchmark stability in flow rates, Deliverable 8.

The following Institutes have contributed to this Deliverable 8:

no	Participant Type	Short Name	Organisation legal full name	Country
13	External Funded Partner	UMCU	Universitair Medisch Centrum Utrecht	Netherlands
5	Internal Funded Partner	METAS	Eidgenössisches Institut für Metrologie METAS	Switzerland
6	Internal Funded Partner	NEL	TUV SUD Limited	United Kingdom
12	External Funded Partner	THL	Technische Hochschule Lübeck	Germany

The progress within this report covers the Period from 1st June 2019 to the end of November 2022.

1. Introduction

Infusion is one of the most widely used technologies in hospitals. However, administering fluids directly into the bloodstream encompasses many risks. These risks can be classified in risks for medical complications, risks associated with the characteristics of drugs, clinical conditions and size of patients and risks of inaccurate delivery of the fluids. The causes of inaccurate delivery of the fluids can be associated with user mistakes in clinical practice, or by the suboptimal physical alignment of the infusion system setup to its purpose.

In the EMPiR Metrology for Drug Delivery I project, Lucas et al. [1] pointed out in a best practice guide that there are many parties involved in infusion technology. All parties involved exert influence on the actual drugs delivered in clinical practice, sometimes without knowing how these seemingly small decisions affect each other and thus patient safety.

Figure 1. Parties involved in infusion technology. The clinical users and clinical supervisors have a key role in ensuring the patients receive a correct dosage.

In a comprehensive review, Foinard et al [2] mentioned many examples of these risks like the introduction of infections, phlebitis, tissue infiltration or thrombosis (medical complications), drug incompatibilities and physicochemical interaction of drugs with the administration sets. In the review, the authors identified critical parameters influencing the drug mass flow rate of infusion delivery to patients during multidrug infusion. The components of infusion systems that particularly influence the flow rate of medications and fluids being delivered were stressed, and they conclude that clinicians should receive instruction on the fluid dynamics of an IV administration set and so be able to take steps to minimize flow rate changes during IV therapy.

Several authors have identified the role of physical parameters on drug delivery and give basic advice in the form of rules of thumb to prevent dosing errors. The common denominator in these recommendations is that in the end, clinicians should decide how to build a set up that considers both the complex interplay of infusion parameters like flowrate, medication characteristics, width of the therapeutic window and biological half values, and the physical characteristics of the individual setup. However, this is a challenging task. The number of different types of administration sets and

infusion components available is numerous, and many of their key physical characteristics, such as compliance and resistance are not available to the clinicians. Let alone, a clear description of these characteristics and their interplay, fit for medical decision making tailored to the patient's individual needs, is lacking. We found that both manufacturers and users of infusion technology have incomplete understanding of the operation of the complete drug delivery system.

To support doctors and nurses in their task to choose a suitable drug delivery strategy, the EMPIR Metrology for Drug Delivery II project [3] set up a well-defined metrological infrastructure to allow drug delivery device manufacturers to get reliable information on the actual dose at the point of entry in the patient. At the start of the project, a clear path was set in which work packages 1 and 2 should provide the tools to develop a microchip pump and new calibration tools of existing medical devices in work package 3, finally bringing all tools together to design a metrologically sound characterized multi-infusion system for clinical practice.

Figure 2. schematic of Metrology for Drug Delivery Technical Work

At the heart of the assignment is the wish for synergy of complementary fields of science: metrology and physics on the one hand, and medical science on the other hand. If carried out literally, by designing high metrology standards to clinical practice, it would lead to unfeasible guidelines and not help patient safety forward because the different practices of both fields are misunderstood: Where physics and metrology can be practiced under well-controlled and stable lab conditions, the conditions in real life medical practice are often uncontrolled and can be very dynamic.

Furthermore, doctors and nurses are primarily interested in the situation and well-being of their patients, and how the best care can be achieved in a feasible workflow in times of personnel shortage. Different applications call for different approaches, which is clarified more in chapter 4 on guidelines for clinical practice. And, for many clinical applications, clinicians tend not to care so much in stabilizing or controlling flow rates, because there are more pressing issues in patient treatment, especially in critical care. The challenge is therefore not to fall into despair, but to bridge the gap between traceability and reality. The best results can be achieved if the parties involved in drug delivery and patient safety are joined, while optimally employing their complementary roles. In such an approach, the clinical responsibility is left to the discretion of the physician, and medication safety guidance to pharmacists, whereas the nurses' responsibility lies in prioritizing care actions according to the urgency and needs of the patients. The clinicians can identify the specific applications of interest that need a stable delivery, thus providing stable blood concentrations.

Subsequently, clinical physicists and engineers should translate these clinical questions to necessary flow rate accuracies and share these with metrologists and manufacturers. Manufacturers can develop new techniques that find to the most clinically relevant questions and provide metrologists with one or more full multi-infusion setups for typical applications, to assess the accuracy of the entire system. The role of metrology would be to independently test these systems to find out what the dynamics of the system are, including the effects of clinical manipulations. Such a multidisciplinary effort could add a lot to patient safety.

Bearing this in mind, we chose to focus on modelling and prediction of flowrates and dosing errors from typical medication schedules, and from there provide guidelines that take clinical practice into account.

Based on the analytical model by Konings et al. [4], the interaction of set up parameters like number of combined flows, set flow rates and administration set characteristics is described in this best practice guide. Mathematical modelling and metrology are used to bridge the knowledge gap by designing a representative multi-infusion system to test how different liquids mix and how this affects drug concentration. This improves the understanding of users of infusion technology regarding the specific equipment they use. The exact consequences of technical choices made on dosing accuracy could be clarified to the healthcare provider by referring to the three most important physical effects influencing drug delivery as explained by Konings⁴:

4. The effects of the composition of the dead volume after the mixing point of constituent flows
5. The compliance and resistance of the infusion setup.
6. The effect of flow development (Poiseuille effect)

In this project, we found that everyday choices in clinical practice, like flow rate adaptations or the choice to use a specific disposable, can influence dosing accuracy [5], [6]. Moreover, the impact of adding components to a multi-infusion setup were investigated with respect to these effects.

Based on this research, it was clarified which requirements a best practice for a multi-infusion system containing check valves, inline sensors or air bubbles should meet. Furthermore, a survey was made on the options to test how liquids, with different viscosities mix and flow and how this affects drug concentration.

2. Clinical and pharmaceutical aspects determining drug delivery

In clinical practice, operational choices are made regarding the administration of drugs by infusion. The clinical reasons to use infusion pumps have a more practical nature and both manufacturers and metrologists should be aware that clinical practice brings along a substantial lower flow rate accuracy than can be reached in a standardized infusion test, e.g., test results according to NEN-ISO-60-601-1. The goals of physicians' medication treatment are to maximize the effectiveness and minimize the risks of treatment and minimize costs and workload per patient.

Some examples of the goals a physician or nurse wants to achieve by using an infusion pump for drug delivery are:

- ✓ Easy implementation to minimize the workload
- ✓ Assure continuous dosing to minimize risks
- ✓ Improving safety by automating error sensitive operations
- ✓ Lack of skilled personnel to carry out alternative treatments not needing a pump

However, using a pump could introduce alternative error forms and an infusion device can only take over a small part of the care given by a skilled nurse. Therefore, not all goals are directly met by using an infusion pump instead of using simple gravity infusion.

The influence of pharmaceuticals on drug delivery and the impact of attained accuracy in drug delivery is very large. Drugs have different characteristics, that determine if dosing accuracy has a major influence on their effectivity. A key concept of interest in necessary accuracy in drug delivery is the pharmacodynamics, the clinical effect of a drug on a patient. It determines clinically important parameters such as time to effect, stability of flow, half-life (elimination, redistribution) of drug within therapeutic range.

The therapeutic range or therapeutic window (TW) is the range of drug concentrations in which a drug is effective. The TW can be defined as the ratio between:

Figure 3. Therapeutic window

- The minimum effective concentration (MEC), which is the minimum concentration that is required for drug effect, and,
- The Minimum toxic concentration (MTC), which is the minimum concentration in which toxicity usually occurs

If you have a low dose for the drug to start working (MEC) and a high dose at which the drug is toxic (MTC) you have a wide window in which the drug can safely be used (TW). Therapeutic windows get smaller with higher doses when the effectivity and toxicity curves

approach each other. The elimination time from the blood is defined as the time needed to eliminate it from the circulation either in an unaltered form (unbound molecules) or modified as a metabolite.

The plasma half-life T_{half} or half-life of elimination is the time required to eliminate 50% of the absorbed dose of a drug from the blood. This is a measure of the drug's residence time in the body.

Figure 4. Elimination time and half-life

Figure 5. Development of serum concentration at sequential bolus injections

The residence time of a drug affects concentration in the serum (and other sites in the body) and on the ideal frequency of administration. The steady state or stable concentration is reached when the drug's supply to the blood plasma is the same as the rate of elimination from the plasma. It is necessary for a pharmacist or physician to calculate this concentration to decide what the period between doses and the amount of drug supplied with each dose in prolonged treatments.

In case of drug delivery via sequential injections the serum concentration develops after every bolus to a maximum concentration and subsequently diminishes in time as is shown in figure 5.

Half-lives of drugs can range from several minutes to several days. A list of half-lives of commonly used drugs and typically used flowrates is given in Table 1. Adding complexity is the fact that drug metabolites can have clinical effects as well. For simplicity's sake here we only state the half-life for elimination of the original drug from the patient's circulation. We advise to do further research into the exact contextual relation of these aspects of drug delivery.

Table 1: half-lives and typical clinical flow rates of commonly used drugs for infusion

Drug	Elimination Half-life	Commonly used flowrates*		Commonly used mass flow rates* *Flowrates are very much dependent on drug concentration and application µg/ kg /min** **different quantities mentioned in cell
		hour	ml/h	
Nitro-glycerine	2	0,03	1-12	5-200
(Nor)epinephrine	1-3	0,03	1-72	0,03-1
Dobutamine	2	0,03	1,2-48	1-20
Esmolol	9	0,15	12-200	50-300
Nitropruside	2-3	0,03	1-15	0,3-10
insulin	6	0,1	2-12	Based on blood sugar value: 0,013-0,1 IE/kg/hr
Midazolam	90-150	1,5-2,5	1-30	0,03-0,2 µg/ kg /hr
Glucagon	12	0,2	12,5 – 37,5	2,5-7,5 mg/hr
Heparin	30	0,5	1-6,4	20.000- 40.000 IE/ 24hr, conc 500 IE/ml
Lidocaine	90	1,5	1-15	0,5-6 mg/kg/h

When combining the pharmaceutical concepts, we find that the effect of a drug reflects its serum concentration. A safer drug has a larger therapeutic range, combining a very large lethal dose to a very small effective dose. On the other hand, a more dangerous drug has a smaller therapeutic range, and may require regular monitoring of drug levels. The targeted dose for drug delivery is found in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Optimal drug delivery within the therapeutic window

Whereas the concentration of drug represented by the blue curve is too low to have effect, the dose of the red curve is too high. The medication dose should be such that the serum concentration follows the green dotted curve to exert its optimal effect.

As a rule of thumb, the medicines requiring a smooth and continuous drug delivery are drugs with small therapeutic range and/ or short elimination time. These are the drugs of special interest for the MeDDII project. Examples of drugs with a small therapeutic range include aminoglycosides, digoxin, phenytoin, gentamicin, amphotericin, 5-fluoro-urocil and zidovudine. Examples of drugs with a short half-life include (nor) epinephrine, dopamine, nitro-glycerine, nitroprusside and esmolol. These medications are known to belong to the list of drugs most frequently causing adverse events [7], [8].

When carrying out multi-infusion, special care must be given to the fact that changing the flow rate of presumably safe medication, i.e., the drugs with large therapeutic windows and long half-lives, can have impact on the flow rates of high-risk medication. Accuracy should therefore be considered as the combined accuracy of all drug-delivering flows that are mixed into the same line before entering the patient. The physical aspects determining drug delivery and its stability are covered in chapter 3.

3. Physical characteristics determining drug delivery

3.1 Dead volume and push-out effect

One of the more straightforward physical parameters that have a clear impact on dosing errors is the so-called dead volume. For this entity, the dead volume, there are two separate definitions, depending on whether the infusion setup is a single pump infusion setup, or a multi-infusion setup, as is explained directly below:

Single pump infusion: Intuitively, for single pump infusion setups, the definition is clear: the dead volume refers to the internal volume of the infusion set from the connection to the syringe (without the syringe itself) all the way to the distal tip of the catheter inside the patient. This dead volume is important if a *syringe changeover* (containing a new, *different*, medicine-containing solution) takes place: the dead volume is used by the physician to estimate the delay time before the first dose of the new medication effectively enters the patient.

Two rules-of-thumb are important in the case of single pump infusion:

- (i) Dead volume (Design Guideline): The design should be such that the dead volume is as small as possible, in order to reduce the travel time for new medication to arrive into the patient. However: the resistance of the infusion line and catheter should preferably remain low enough to avoid the combined effect of infusion disposable characteristics of resistance and compliance, or RC-effects, that are explained below.
- (ii) Method of estimating the time-of-first-arrival of the new medicine after a syringe changeover: Due to the Poiseuille flow profile, the elapsed time t_{First} between the changeover of the syringe and the arrival of the first dose of new medicine in the blood stream equals:

$$t_{First} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{V_{internal}}{flowrate}\right)$$

in which the extra factor $\frac{1}{2}$ is caused by the Poiseuille effect, and essential for physicians to take notice of.

Multi-infusion: In the case of a multi-infusion set-up, the above-mentioned rules-of-thumb apply as well. In addition to these rules, the presence of Dead Volume produces a specific effect that comes to light in a multi-infusion set-up only. This specific effect is called the push-out effect, as is explained directly below. For this specific effect, the push-out effect, the definition of the Dead Volume is the volume of the tubing or catheter starting from the Mixing Point M (see figure 7 below) and ending in the distal tip P inside the patient:

Figure 7*: Schematic, illustrating the push-out effect, i.e.: the temporary increase in the outflow of the red fluid into the patient due to an increase in speed of the blue pump, as is explained below.

a Two infusion pumps, filled with a blue and a red solution, respectively, produce the same flow rate, which is constant in time. The two flows are merged at the mixing point M , and subsequently travel towards point P , which represents the distal tip of the catheter where the fluid enters the blood stream of the patient. Since the flow rates of both pumps are equal, the catheter from point M to point P contains equal amounts of red and blue fluid, in the form of a mixture. This mixture is travelling with a flow rate that is twice the flow rate of each pump. A constant amount r of red fluid is entering the patient during each unit time interval (illustrated by a canister at point P for each unit time interval).

b The same set-up, but now, at $t = 0$, the flow rate of the blue pump is suddenly increased by a factor 5. As a result, after $t = 0$, the amount of red fluid entering the patient at point P now temporarily equals $3r$ per unit time. Therefore, in **b**, the memory effect is visible: the distal part of the catheter (near P) still contains the old mixing ratio corresponding to the situation before $t = 0$. This old mixture is now being pushed out at the new speed; hence we dubbed this temporary increase in output of red fluid the push-out effect. In the literature, this effect is sometimes referred to as dead volume effect, or catheter memory effect. **c** After $t = t_{\text{delay}}$, the amount of red fluid entering the blood stream per unit time equals r again, which equals the intended dose, just like the situation before $t = 0$ in **a**

*figure from: Konings *et al. BioMed Eng OnLine* (2017) 16:18⁴

As a result, from the Push-out effect described in the figure directly above, the following guideline can be formulated:

- (iii) Push-out effect: Be aware that a temporary overdose (or underdose) of a certain critical medication can occur, even if the flow rate settings of the pump of that specific critical medication has not been altered. This temporary dosing error is caused by the push-out effect after a change in flow rate settings at another pump and is exacerbated if the internal volume between points M and P (the dead volume in figure 1 directly above) is large.

3.2 System mechanical compliance and resistance

Infusion systems can have multiple compressible parts, that can influence the flowrate. They can be found in the pump itself, the holding frame and in all disposable infusion sets and syringes.

Syringe

Infusion lines

Filters

The pump itself

Figure 8. Examples of sources of compliance in an infusion setup.

The mechanical compressibility of the rubber plungers in syringes is generally the main source of mechanical compliance in today's clinically used infusion set-ups (both single pump infusion and multi-infusion). Mechanical compliance is defined as the increase of internal volume divided by pressure increase. Its mathematical symbol is C and, combines with the flow resistance R to yield the RC time (simple multiplication of R and C), which represents the typical time scale on which the above-mentioned increase of internal volume is released again if the pressure drops. In the following, directly below, the effects of mechanical compliance are discussed for single pump infusion and multi-infusion, respectively.

Single pump infusion: In a single pump infusion set-up, the mechanical compliance gives rise to an additional delay (in the order of R times C , i.e. the RC -time mentioned above) after a syringe exchange, or, more generally, whenever a pump is restarted: during the pressure build-up in the infusion line directly after the (re)start of the pump, the plunger in the syringe will be compressed, thereby causing the extra delay in the build-up of the flow rate.

A simple way of visualizing the effect of compliance upon flowrate doubling is shown in figure 9.

Whereas the mechanical compliance is hard to avoid, the RC-time is equally influenced by the resistance R of the system. The resistance R of a tube is inversely proportional to the fourth power of its diameter. From investigations by e.g., Snijder et al [9] it has been shown that especially very thin catheters (1 French) can give rise to clinically detrimental RC times due to the very high flow resistance (having values up to $R = 1.95 \text{ kPa}/(\text{ml}/\text{h})$) of these very thin catheters, whereas the R values of thicker catheters (4 French and more) do not give rise to clinically significant RC-times.

Apart from the tubing diameter, there are more components commonly part of infusion set ups of high resistance. Commonly known high resistance parts are check valves, that have high opening pressures, filters containing very small pores and needle free valves (SmartSites) for infection prevention.

Check valves

Filters

Multi-lumen catheters 1-3 Fr

SmartSites[®]

Figure 10. High resistance elements of infusion sets

Flow resistance values of typical infusion setup components were measured at NEL and METAS and are given in table 2.

Table 2: flow resistance of commonly used components in multi-infusion setups

Component	Type	Flow resistance (Pa/(mL/h))	Start up pressure for opening (Pa)	Internal volume (micro L)
Check valve	NRV from IV Slotset Neo	987 ± 50	14000 ± 1000	
Anti Siphon Valve	BD Ref 04302260452	150 ± 50	14000 ± 1000	200
Central catheter	Various types	7 - 200	n/a	
Umbilical catheter	VYCON Ref 1270.04 4 Fr (ID 0.8 mm, OD 1.5 mm, L 40 cm)	10 ± 1	n/a	360
Infusion line	BD Ref G40020B (L 200 cm, vol 1.4 mL)	33.3 ± 1.7	n/a	1400
Infusion line	VYCON Ref 71100.20 (ID 1 mm, OD 2 mm, L 200 cm, vol 2.0 mL)	16.0 ± 0.8	n/a	2000
Air filter	Pall Medical Filter Ref NEO96E (0.2 micro, vol 0.4 mL)	78.0 ± 4.0	n/a	400
Check valve	NRV from IV Slotset Neo	987 ± 50	14000 ± 1000	
Density and viscosity sensor	Conventional Viscosity Measurement System of BHT	1700 ± 60	n/a	> 400

Resistance has also an effect on the system pressure and as a result, on the pressure of the system. As occlusion pressures for most syringe pumps are not directly measured but derived from the force exerted on the syringe plunger, both clinicians and hospital technicians should be aware of the resistances in infusion set-ups when determining occlusion pressure settings. We therefore formulate the following guidelines:

- (iv) Effect of mechanical compliance in single pump infusion:
 - Be aware of the significant extra delay in drug delivery into the patient after syringe exchange, or, more generally, any pump restart, especially when using components of high resistance like thin catheters.
 - Avoid adding high resistance elements to setups for non-clinical purposes, for example flow sensors, especially when using low flow rates and fast-acting medications with small therapeutic ranges.
- (v) Effect of resistance on the occurrence of occlusion pressure alarms:
 - Be aware of pressure increasing effects of highly resistant components of the infusion setup and set the occlusion pressure limits accordingly to prevent inadvertent alerting.

Connection of effects

- Many components are added to an infusion setup for safety reasons. Smart site connectors for example should prevent both hospital infections for the patient and bloodborne needle stick injuries for the caregiver. At the same time, they add resistance to the system, thus adding to the start-up time of an infusion therapy.

Multi-infusion: The effect of mechanical compliance is especially complicated and potentially clinically dangerous in a multi-infusion set-up. In contrast to the single pump infusion case, the mechanical compliance effect is interfering with the push-out effect (see point (iii) above), and, even more seriously, altering the resulting flow rate in a direction opposite to that of the push-out effect. This can give rise to temporary dosing errors that are both counter-intuitive and confusing for the physician. This is illustrated in figure 11:

a) Push-out effect
before tip of
Poiseuille profile of
new mixture
reaches the patient

b) Push-out effect
after tip of Poiseuille
profile of new
mixture reaches the
patient

c) Effect of
mechanical
compliance

Figure 11. Simultaneous occurrence of the push-out effect and effect of mechanical compliance

In a multi-infusion set-up, the push-out effect and the effect of mechanical compliance can occur simultaneously after $\tau = 0$ (in which $\tau = 0$ corresponds to the moment in time that the tip of the Poiseuille profile reaches the patient). In all situations, however, the sign of the dosing error of the push-out effect will be *opposite* to the sign of the effect of mechanical compliance (see (b) and (c), in this case where the sign is negative and positive respectively). Therefore, it depends on the relative strengths of the push-out effect and mechanical compliance whether the net total effect (after $\tau = 0$) will be a dosing error resulting in decreased or increased dosage. This makes the combination of these two effects hard to predict, and potentially counter-intuitive and confusing for the physician.

Multi-infusion (cont'd): On the basis of the explanation given in figure 2 directly above, the following guideline can be formulated:

- (vi) Since the total net effect of push-out effect and mechanical compliance effect in a multi-infusion can be demonstrably confusing and hard to predict, it is desirable that the clinician does not jump to conclusions based on perceived reactions of the patient to changes in administered flow rates, especially directly after the time lapse of $\tau = t_{first}$ after the change in pump flow rate settings, in which

$$t_{First} = \left(\frac{1}{2}\right) \left(\frac{V_{internal}}{flowrate}\right)$$

Combined effects of push out, resistance and compliance, both single pump and multi-infusion:

- (vii) As a rule of thumb: if the internal diameter of the catheter is smaller than 2 millimetres, then RC-effects need to be taken into account.
- (viii) Besides being aware and vigilant concerning these counter-intuitive net effects of the combination of push-out and mechanical compliance effects in multi-infusion, physicians may use a bed-side predictions tool (small computer attached to the multi-infusion set-up) that provides insight into the dosing errors that are to be expected after syringe exchange or changes in pump flow rate settings. Such a bed-side prediction tool is currently in development (see figure 12 below).

Figure 12. Results presented on the screen of the predictive tool

In the figure, top-left the two-pump system is described. In this example, the set flowrate of pump A is changed. In 'Materials' the syringes and mixing points that are used can be selected from the drop-down menus. The impact of changing the set flowrate on pump A on the resulting flow of the substance in pump B at the vascular access point is presented in the different figures. In the top-right the total dosing errors is shown. The bottom-left figure shows the set flow rate (yellow) and the actual flow rate (purple) of the critical medication from pump B. The bottom-right figure shows the contribution of different factors to the deviation from the set flow rate of pump B.

To include the pharmaceutical aspects of drug delivery, guidelines should consider the combined effect of these aspects and physical effects. Mathematically, this can be seen as a convolution of physical and chemical system characteristics. As protocolized flowrates are very much dependent on drug concentration and application, we advise clinicians to the following guideline:

- (ix) Minimise differences in drug concentrations used for infusion, by defining standardised used concentrations [10], [11], [12], especially for the drugs requiring a stable blood concentration.

3.3. Air Bubbles

The presence of air bubbles in a (multi-)infusion set-up *in combination with an air filter* gives rise to a time delay interval during which the drug delivery is temporarily stopped until all air has escaped through the air filter. In addition to this, it also possibly causes an unexpected and large occurrence of the above-mentioned effect of mechanical compliance.

This is explained directly below in the two phenomena that are largely unknown to the medical staff.

- (a) If air bubbles are removed from the infusion line using an air filter, then an unexpectedly large extra delay in drug delivery may be created owing to pressure effects in combination with compressibility (mechanical compliance) of syringes.
- (b) if there is no air filter present and hence air bubbles are not filtered out, then the presence of even very small air bubbles may have a profound effect on the time needed, after a syringe exchange with a new medication into the pump, for the first molecules of the new medication to arrive at the patient, owing to a distortion of the Poiseuille flow profile.

More information on phenomenon (a): as described above in section 2.2 (Mechanical Compliance), there is an additional delay in the delivery of the medication to the patient of the order of the RC-time if a pump is started. The essential point that we address in this guide is that *this same start-up phenomenon will also occur directly after an air bubble has escaped through an air filter* in the infusion set-up. An air filter in an infusion line is equipped with microscopic orifices that allow air to escape to the environment but keeps liquids inside. If an air bubble is present inside the infusion line near the pump, it will travel along with the fluid through the infusion line, until it reaches the air filter. Once the air bubble enters the air filter, the air escapes immediately to the environment, giving rise to a *sudden pressure drop* in the part of the infusion line between the pump and the air filter, which in turn causes the compressible part of the plunger of the syringe to relax into its original unpressurized state. As a result, the actual flowrate of the fluid entering the bloodstream of the patient drops as well and needs time to be restored.

More information on phenomenon (b): in case that an air bubble is present inside an infusion system that does *not* incorporate an air filter, a different mechanism can still take place. Any tiny air bubble that is still large enough to cover the whole cross-sectional area of a (thin) catheter or infusion line will prevent the development of a complete Poiseuille flow profile throughout the catheter or infusion line (see Figure 13 directly below).

Figure 13. Photographical illustration of the effect of an air bubble in an infusion line

Description of figure 13

a) medication from a new syringe (blue dye in this photograph), entering the infusion line directly after a syringe exchange, is trapped behind an air bubble. The direction of the flow is from left to right in this picture. Length of the air bubble is about 1 cm. Distance between grid lines on the paper in the background is 5 mm. The old medication (transparent, without dye), pumped into the infusion line before the syringe exchange, is still present inside the infusion line directly next to the air bubble at the right side of the bubble. The flow rate was 20 ml/h.

b) As in (a), but without an air bubble, allowing a Poiseuille flow profile to develop.

c) As in (b), still without air bubble, but now after a longer period, and farther from the entrance of the infusion line, showing further development downstream.

Single pump infusion and multi-infusion:

Hence, based on the explanation directly above, we formulate the following guideline:

- (x) Even in case of an air filter, do try to avoid the emergence of air bubbles in the infusion set-up, because the mechanical compliance effect can give rise to unexpected extra delays in drug delivery, especially when working with thin catheters

More information on the effect of the presence of an air bubble, inside an infusion line, on the time (T_{new}) needed for a new medication to reach the patient after a syringe exchange can be found in a comprehensive paper by Konings e.a. [13] prepared for the special issue of Biomedical Engineering on Medical flow and dosing measurement metrology in drug delivery.

3.4 Measurement components, inline sensors, check valves

In the light of the effects explained above (push-out effect, Poiseuille profile effect, and mechanical compliance effect) a set of guidelines can be derived for the introduction of extra components, such as inline sensors, check valves (anti-reflux valves) and other measuring devices, into the infusion set-up:

Single pump infusion and multi-infusion:

Special attention should be paid to the potential introduction of extra dead volume, extra resistance R , or extra mechanical compliance C into the set-up owing to the addition of additional components. Hence, we formulate the following guidelines:

- (xi) Flow meters: It has been found that flow meters, attached to the end of the catheter, may have such a high internal flow resistance that they can produce unexpectedly high RC times in the system as extra delay in start-up phenomena.
- (xii) Inline sensors: special care should be given to the assessment of the order of magnitude of the additional internal flow resistance R due to the introduction of inline sensors. Inline measurement of concentration for that reason seems not to add to patient safety.
- (xiii) Check Valves: Be aware that check valves may have a considerable extra internal volume, which may exacerbate the push-out effect considerably. An elaborate model on the effect of non-return valves on the time-of-arrival of new medication in a patient after syringe exchange in an infusion set-up exchange can be found in a comprehensive paper by Konings e.a. [14] prepared for the special issue of Biomedical Engineering on Medical flow and dosing measurement metrology in drug delivery.

4. Multi-infusion measurement

To characterize flow rates in a multi-infusion system, a both a setup under investigation and a measurement system must be defined.

Figure 14. Schematic showing the measurement system design discriminating the measurement system and setup under examination

Within the Metrology for Drug Delivery I [15] project an in-vitro setup was developed to illustrate the push-out effect and the effect of system mechanical compliance [16]. A schematic of the measurement principle can be found in figure 15.

Figure 15. Schematic visualisation of the multi-infusion measurement set-up. (1) syringe pumps (2) infusion lines (3) manifold (either: A, B or C) (4) flow-cell (5) laser (light source) (6) spectrometer (7) computer for spectrometer data storage (8) Container for output of flow on a mass balance (9) computer for balance data

The setup under examination can be changed according to the measurement needs. In figure 15 three options for the set-up under examination are proposed according to its task to investigate mixing and drug concentration for various clinical applications: setup A contains a y connector catheter; set-up B uses a BD connector and set-up C a prototype component.

At the beginning of the project, a test matrix was defined for three clinically realistic setups, based on a literature review and clinician interviews. A fully integrated mass flow, pressure, density and viscosity sensor, developed by Bronckhorst High Tech [17] was integrated in one of the setups to add traceability of the flow rate of each component, and thus of the medication dose.

One of the challenges in the joint effort of metrologists and health professionals to improve dosing accuracy of individual medications in a multi-infusion setup, is the difference in level of characterisation of these two parts of the setup. Whereas metrologists can specify and ensure stable lab conditions, the real-life setup under examination is not so well-characterised and at times also very dynamic.

Moreover, parts of the measurement system can influence the setup under investigation in such a way that the measurement can't give an adequate representation of it anymore. This was unfortunately true for the multiparameter sensor setup that was tested during this project. Though the setup had the capacity to measure viscosities and flow rates of different drugs inline in a mixture, because of its high resistance, it wasn't clinically representative. Measurement systems for use in clinical practice need to adapt their physical characteristics in such a way that they don't interfere with clinical requirements such as minimal start-up times. For clinical practice, the accuracy needed from the sensors might be lower than can be achieved with these high-tech apparatuses as medical practice itself can be less accurate.

Therefore, we chose to return to the measurement system using dyes and spectrophotometry that can deliver qualitative information on how infusion liquids mix and flow upon changes that are representative for clinical practice. These setups were developed at THL and UMC Utrecht.

In figure 16 the setup used at THL is shown.

Figure 16. Picture of the multi-infusion measurement set-ups 1 and 3 at THL. (left) Neonatal setup using 3 syringe pumps and a dedicated Neoset (right) Paediatric setup using 3 syringe pumps and a manifold

A replica of the neonatal setup was sent to NEL for metrological characterization. These measurements can be used for the validation of models that predict how liquids with different characteristics mix and flow, and how this affects the effective drug concentration over the time of delivery. Distinct effects that were modelled can easily be visualised using dyes, such as the Poiseuille effect in figure 13 b and c.

In this way, measurements and modelling can bring a clear understanding to the clinical user of how changes in infusion pump settings and set-ups influence the stability of patient dose. If the specific medication requires dosing stability, the clinician can adapt the settings accordingly.

A preferred way to share the outcome of metrological measurements is to use them in hands-on workshops where participants can try out the workings of physical characteristics of the multi-infusion systems on real-life clinical setups using simple model fluids like water, milk, and coffee. Such a workshop was done at ESICM 35th LIVES conference at Paris for the Nurses and Allied Health Personnel community and was well-liked by both nurses, pharmacists, doctors, and manufacturers.

Figure 17. Impression of the ESICM LIVES workshop on multi-infusion.

5. Best practices

A best practice guide on how to build an optimized multi-infusion set-up to ensure the most effective dosing of a combination of drugs has two typical recipients: clinical users and manufacturers. Guidelines how to build a multi-infusion setup start from the patient needs. From there, choices must be made that balance clinical needs, pharmaceutical boundary conditions and the knowledge of metrological and physical principles found in this project. In this chapter guidelines are given that are applicable for general infusion therapy as well as guidelines that are connected to some specific patient applications.

5.1. General clinical considerations

1. The multi-infusion setup should protect the patient from suboptimal environmental conditions and unnecessary interruptions of rest or sleep.
2. For small paediatric or neonatology patients, be aware of patient characteristics of small patients and their consequences on the physical multi-infusion setup. This holds especially for awareness of the concept of development-oriented concepts of care in neonatology and paediatrics: care is focused on the developmental needs, minimizing the detrimental effects of the physical stimuli accompanying medical care. Here, the concern of the patient is the wish to sleep without disturbances and are protected against receiving all alarms next to their head. Neonates are treated in incubators stabilizing environment, which bring boundary conditions to the set-up that can be used.
3. Within these conditions, the best choices should be made to set up the system according to the guidelines in chapter 3. Long term paediatric cancer patients rest preferably without noise of alarms and changes of medication by the nurses. This creates the wish that IV lines are long to make placement outside the room possible.
4. Tailor the setup to patient workflow. One should understand the sequence in care, e.g., in oncology: morning lab round (8:00), ward round of the doctor with the lab results (10:00-11:00), go for chemotherapy, order to the pharmacy (11:00-12:00), delivering chemotherapy (14:00-15:00) and then infusions go for the next 10-12 hours
5. The improvement of the general safety of drug delivery needs to be addressed in a multidisciplinary team approach that makes use of the complementary roles of all professionals involved. The clinician is overall responsible on a case-to-case patient because of the observed individual effect of the treatment and the individual safety of the treatment, and can ask their technical counterparts for intercollegial consultation; guidance of the pharmacists in medication safety and guidance of (clinical) physicists, manufacturers and metrologists in technical conditions and setup
6. Treat drugs with short halftime different from drugs with long halftime:
 - Put the drugs with short half-time closer to the patient
 - more fixed on height (to prevent gravity-induced dosing variations)
 - less filters or other resistance increasing materials
7. Technical experts such as manufacturers, physicists and metrologists should be working together with clinicians to be aware of specific characteristics of drugs and their effect on necessary flowrate accuracy. E.g., all (almost all) drugs giving intravenously in (paediatric) cancer patients are long action and not specific time driven drugs. Healthcare professionals want the infusions to start and end within a time window. For these therapies, a little delay because of the length of the IV lines is not critical for patient safety and therefore is not their first concern.

8. However, as soon as long infusion lines are used for multi-infusion of long action drugs with another drug that is time driven or has a short elimination time, potential harmful situations can arise. Therefore, multi-infusion of time-driven drugs with short elimination times on long lines should be avoided and clinical teams need to be educated in this knowledge.
9. As a rule of thumb: Keep lines as short as possible, but if you create more length use lines with less resistance or valves to get real pressure alarming.
10. More research should be done using the combined expertise of both clinicians, clinical physicists, metrologists, and pharmacists to define standardised set-up protocols that optimally balance the needed infusion set component characteristics to specific applications. This interdisciplinary group should ask manufacturers to help find alternative solutions to accomplish the desirable healing environment, for instance by making use of remote controls.
11. Reconsider if a/ changes of continuous infusion is necessary during patient rest periods, for instance during the night.
12. If multi-infusion can be prevented or minimized of the amount of multi medications on one line, use a separate line, e.g., adult ICU inotropes can quite easily used on a separate line; access is easier.
13. Educate users of multi-infusion on the lessons learned from metrology using both practical hands-on training with set-ups used in clinical practice and visualisation tools that can predict the outcome of practice-based medication schedules.

5.2 Guidance on specific multi-infusion situations in clinical practice

Building the multi-infusion setup

1. Avoid combinations of high and low flow rate medications on the same lumen. If using a carrier flow with higher flow rate, always be aware of push out effects when stopping low flow rates of fast acting drugs with small therapeutic ranges and low elimination times.
2. Attach the medications with shortest half-lives proximally (closest) to the patient
3. When using inotropes or other drugs with low elimination times that need a stable blood concentration, as low compliant syringes as possible should be used – use smaller size syringes if possible.
4. Make sure that the syringe is pressurized before starting the flow
5. Carefully weigh the pros and cons of set up choices:
 - During anaesthesia the IV lines are longer because they are all below the sterile blankets of the surgeon. The use of air filters or IV lines for separate use is with risk for stops in the line where you can't reach these points.
 - During transport to the MRI, long lines are quite often required to keep the pumps out of the MRI or they are secured in a MRI docking which makes it difficult for the clinician to alter the medication when it needs to be.
6. Renew multi-setup medication setups in clinical setting preferable in the day with clinical supervision on the impact of the patient responses.

Starting the infusion

7. Beware of the RC effect and make sure that the syringe is under pressure before starting the flow.

Transporting a patient

8. Height effects lead to pressure effects lead to RC effects. Prevent height differences when using drugs with short elimination times.

Changeover of vasoactive drug infusions

To reduce alterations in plasma concentration clinicians have experimented with methods colloquially known as 'double pumping' or 'piggybacking' [18], [19], [20]: a method in which the same drug is running simultaneously in two infusions. One of these infusions will be near completion while the second replacement infusion is introduced by means of a multiway stopcock, e.g., a three-way tap. It is commonly thought within the clinical community that skill and experience with this technique are necessary both to prevent over or under infusion of the intravenous vasoactive medication and to manage any alterations in blood pressure and heart rate during the procedure.

However, our project outcome suggests that besides that as an additional guideline to minimize syringe exchange instability:

9. To attain safe changeover of vasoactive drug infusions preferably the pump should automatically provide a relay system that both minimizes the duration of and accurately measures the double dosing time so that the accurate and safe functioning can be verified objectively. In this way, the clinician is relieved of this task of guessing these parameters during an already demanding job.
10. Furthermore, doctors, with the aid of pharmacists, can establish guidelines for maximum acceptable double dosing times to be given as input for infusion pump manufacturers.

Specific guidelines for small patients

11. Be aware that small children and neonates because of their size typically need small and thus high resistance catheters and its implications on time delays (RC effects) and occlusion pressure settings. As a rule of thumb, if the internal diameter of the catheter is smaller than 2 millimetres, then RC-effects need to be considered. This implicates that under these conditions it is important to
 - Make sure the syringe is pressurized before starting the flow
 - Adapt pressure settings to the system total resistance
12. Be aware that certain diseases prompt the clinicians to actions that have a negative effect on flowrate variability and thus dosing stability. For a NICU patient with still patent ductus arteriosus small air emboli create a risk for the new-born brain and air filters are introduced. The downside is the resistance and the necessity to introduce a separate line for fat emulsions and some other medications.
13. Build the IV setup taking all boundary conditions into consideration, for example:
 - PICU neonate direct after cardiac surgery; one double lumen central line and one peripheral IV line; one line used for inotropes like epinephrine and milrinone combined with sedatives as morphine, one central venous pressure line (short bolus of medication are given here as well). Peripheral IV is used for boluses of fluids and blood products.
 - NICU patient the accuracy is needed for especially inotropes with short half-life, air bubbles need to be minimized and length to get into the incubator is needed

5.3 Guidelines for manufacturers

In the process of delivery of a drug multiple brands are involved. Manufacturers should be aware of the place of their product in the traceability chain of drug delivery. This holds for the manufactures of the pumps, who were primarily involved in this project, but is equally important for syringe, line, and stopcocks manufacturers. We advise manufacturers to adhere to the following guidelines:

- i. Manufactures need to make sure their products provide an accurate, but more important a stable, constant flow in the delivery of a drug. To do so, they should
 - a. Take notice of:
 - i. the clinical environment where their products are placed
 - ii. the effect of the physical characteristics of their products on drug delivery.
 - b. Implement in their product design:
 - i. Knowledge on clinical aims, provided by doctors
 - ii. Information on hospital workflow, provided by nurses and other health care staff
 - iii. Characteristics that minimize resistance and internal volume:
 1. Design Guideline: The design should be such that the dead volume is as small as possible, to reduce the travel time for new medication to arrive into the patient,
 2. Design Guideline: the resistance of an infusion component should preferably remain low enough to avoid RC-effects using the guidelines from chapter 3.
 - c. Interact with manufacturers of other products used in the infusion setups used in clinical practice, and together provide typical multi-infusion set-ups to high end calibration facilities to indepently assess the physical parameters of interest for dosing stability, and share this information with customers and other manufacturers, particularly:
 - i. Internal volume
 - ii. Resistance:
 - iii. Compliance
 - iv. Stick-slip information
 - v. The diameter of the syringe can be easily recognized
 - d. Help clinicians find alternative strategies to
 - i. long infusion lines for implementing infusion therapy in patient isolation rooms that consider both patient centred care needs and the workflow demands by implementing new technology tailored to the needs in clinical practice
 - ii. using small syringes to achieve low compliance that consider both the usability in the pump and the minimization of syringe exchanges
 - iii. excessive alarming that causes both a disturbance of the healing environment and create alarm tiredness in healthcare providers for preventing errors

6. Conclusions: What metrology can do to improve dosing accuracy

The Metrology for Drug Delivery II project provided new tools improving the traceability chain in drug delivery. Determining the accuracy of a specific parameter of the pump in a laboratory is only a small part of the traceability chain in drug delivery. But this is an important step to identify and correct the error of the device. This is the main role of National Metrology Institutes and Accredited laboratories.

In this Best Practice Guide, the partners of the Metrology for Drug Delivery II project set the first step in bridging the gap between traceability to first standards under well-determined laboratory conditions and less determined dynamic conditions in clinical reality.

When the device is installed in the clinical environment several characterization tests can be performed using inline sensors or even simulations. Another possibility is that an end user asks for a specific characterization of the drug delivery devices, at specific points, quantities, liquids characteristics, ambient conditions, and disposable components to NMIs, Accredited laboratories or even the manufacturers. This will lead to a most real delivery accuracy before the entrance of the drug into the patient. The metrological periodicity of tests of the device should be established by the user with the help of NMIs and manufacturers, since now there is no regulations or standards defining this.

Manufacturers, NMIs and end users should all work together to improve the dosing accuracy and prevent morbidity due to the devices/delivery systems. Each actor has its place in the traceability chain, and this should be well established for the benefit of the patient.

An important task for the partners of the consortium and the EURAMET is to show the knowledge of MEDD II to clinicians and other end-users, by

- Sharing reports with the lessons learned in the MEDD II to clinicians
- Providing workshops and hands-on training to clinicians and other end-users
- Start the conversation in a multidisciplinary team and create a system approach tailored to the different needs of the clinical settings (not a need of the patient based)

Physicists and medical engineers in hospitals can deliver a first line consultation on the technical conditions needed for adequate drug delivery close to its day-to-day application, and construct models for estimating the actual doses. Metrologists can validate these models and provide reliable quantitative actual data on drug dosage available for all delivered drugs simultaneously under well-defined lab conditions. Manufacturers can add to this effort by both providing products for characterisation of the physical characteristics and use this information to improve their products.

For the future, we can go forward if we understand that parts of the problems of the current medical pumps can be addressed in the future development of the pumps by the manufacturers. This journey starts from the awareness that the clinical use as described in the clinical cases all have some pump properties in common which could be optimized. Improvements in alarm management, the possibility for remote control of pumps at the bedside and the prevention of unnecessary stimuli in a healing patient environment would make the placement of pumps closer to the bedside possible. This would facilitate not only the use of shorter lines and thus more accuracy in delivery but also create possibilities for bedside safety measurements. From the understanding that the drug is for the patient, but the device is in control of the healthcare provider new devices can be designed based on the different needs of these important end users.

With this guide, the Metrology for Drug Delivery II Project has now provided the necessary tools to go forward in this direction of cooperative effort of developing conditions for safe drug delivery.

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